

Silicone Bleeding of all types and Brands of Silicone and Saline Breast Implants

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Letter to the Editor

Recently there have been 2 publications that have drawn our attention to silicone Breast Implant Illness (BII), presenting new insights which were not expected and neither were they suspected. It was a surprise to learn that the latest generation of well-regarded modern brands, bleed silicone molecules within 3 weeks after implantation [1] and that saline breast implants with a silicone elastomer shell likewise bleed silicone molecules from the shell into the surrounding capsule after years of implantation [2].

There seems to be a relationship between this bleeding of silicone molecules, which increases exponentially as time goes by and the occurrence of health complaints (Breast Implant Illness, BII).

One may think that anyone is subjected to a decline in health as one ages. However, it becomes different when young women in their thirties present themselves with complaints as if they are in

menopause. What is also remarkable is that the only chance at recovery to a higher or lesser degree, only occurs after explantation of the breast implants [3]. In late cases with many years of implantation the complaints are debilitating and patients become wheelchair bound. In former days, when hardly anything was known about BII, there were late cases with paralysis of the intestines.

We were lucky years ago, when a woman who had silicone breast implants for many years donated her body for scientific analysis. The silicone molecules could be found in every tissue in huge numbers [4]. Although every individual has Si in the body, women with silicone or saline breast implants are in a category of their own.

Research is ongoing to gain greater understanding of the phenomenon of 'bleeding' of breast implants and their effects on health.

References

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